

Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in Relation to Learners' Academic Performance

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Abstract:

This study investigated parental involvement in the Blended Learning Modality and its relation to learners' academic performance in a private school in a large-sized division in Central Philippines during the 2022–2023 school year. Focusing on 200 respondents, it examined variables including age, educational attainment, number of children, and average family monthly income. A descriptive, comparative-correlational design was used, and data were gathered via a researcher-made questionnaire. Statistical tools included frequency count, percentage, mean, Mann-Whitney U test, and Spearman rho. Findings revealed that over half of the parents were high school graduates, had three or more children, and earned Php 12,000 or less monthly. Parental involvement across all areas—home learning environment, motivation, and tutoring—was rated high, with tutoring scoring the highest. Educational attainment and number of children showed high levels of involvement across all areas. Income level also generally indicated high involvement, though parental tutoring scored very high among higher-income families. Learners' academic performance was rated very satisfactory. No significant differences were found between parental involvement and academic performance based on parents' educational attainment. However, significant differences emerged in relation to number of siblings and income level, particularly in the areas of home learning environment, motivation, and tutoring. Overall, the study concluded that while parental involvement was high, it did not significantly affect learners' academic performance in the blended learning setup.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Blended Learning, Parental Involvement

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Parental involvement refers to the active collaboration between families, schools, and communities, aimed at raising awareness of the importance of engaging in children's education and equipping parents with the necessary skills. These partnerships redefine the traditional roles within education by enhancing parental and community capacities and creating an environment where children can learn more effectively. By extending learning beyond the classroom, such collaboration strengthens the overall educational experience (Emerson, 2016). In the context of the new normal, especially during distance learning, parents have taken on more significant and unfamiliar roles, bearing increased responsibility for their children's academic success despite the challenges they face (Garbe, 2020).

This involvement can take various forms, such as home learning activities, direct school participation, and supportive parenting. With growing school enrollment rates, educators are increasingly encouraged to adopt evidence-based strategies to improve family engagement (Van Voorhis, 2016). Research supports the idea that enhancing parental involvement can play a vital role in improving children's early learning outcomes. As such, strategic interventions to strengthen family-school partnerships are seen as essential in promoting learner achievement and fostering a more inclusive and effective educational system.

As a public elementary school teacher, the researcher observed that parental involvement significantly influences students' academic performance. The shift brought by the pandemic transformed parental roles from home-based support to more direct involvement in their children's learning, especially within blended learning environments. However, not all parents possess the skills to teach basic concepts like reading or counting, nor do all homes have the resources to meet learners' needs. These challenges, along with the varying levels of parental understanding and motivation, inspired the researcher to conduct this study to better prepare for and support learners in the blended learning modality.

Current State of Knowledge

Parental involvement plays a crucial role in student success, both in traditional and virtual learning environments. As education shifted online, parents assumed new, often unfamiliar roles with increased responsibility for their children's learning, leading to challenges in defining their involvement (Liu et al., 2010; Garbe et al., 2020). One effective form of involvement is setting academic expectations, which has been shown to significantly enhance student performance (Jeynes, 2016). Collaborative learning activities between parents and children not only support academic growth but also strengthen emotional bonds, helping to reduce anxiety and build comfort during uncertain times (Bhamani, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted the importance of home-school partnerships, as parents balanced work with overseeing education, emphasizing the need for trust-based collaboration between families and schools (Packman, 2020).

Building on this, a study by the State University of New York in Buffalo explored Filipino parental involvement and its influence on children's academic performance, highlighting the deep care, affection, and obedience characteristic of Filipino family dynamics (Tambara, 2016). Despite strong familial bonds, the study emphasized the challenges posed by poverty, unstable employment, and regional disparities, which limit educational opportunities and outcomes. Using a social capital perspective, it noted that family income significantly shapes the level and quality of parental investment in education. Cultural diversity across the archipelago and high fertility rates further complicate consistent parental involvement, often leading to child labor or harsher discipline practices, as reflected in UNICEF's Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (UNICEF, 2015). These challenges were echoed in Northern Mindanao, where educators struggled with remote learning due to pandemic restrictions, lack of access to learning materials, and children's limited reading skills (Luczon, 2020).

International research further reinforces that parental involvement—through school engagement, home support, and academic socialization—significantly improves academic outcomes and emotional well-being. Child development experts from the University of Pittsburgh and the University of Michigan stressed that active parental roles, such as communication with teachers, managing home study, and setting academic goals, are key to success (Pek & Mee, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic intensified parents' educational responsibilities, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, widening educational inequalities (Mizunoya et al., 2020). Shao et al. (2021) found parental involvement increases satisfaction with online learning, influenced by parental education and number of children, while studies from Thailand and China linked engagement more closely to parental education and employment than income (Naite, 2021; Guo et al., 2018). Hara and Burke (2016) emphasized that sustained parent-teacher collaboration, beyond crisis periods, is essential for continuous academic improvement, a view echoed by Kalayci and Oz (2018), who noted positive parental perceptions of involvement across demographics.

Focusing specifically on Filipino families, Agaton and Cueto (2021) revealed that marginalized families faced instructional, financial, and technical barriers during the pandemic, underscoring the need for parent training in digital literacy and home learning strategies. Toggle (2020) found significant links between parental involvement and academic performance, influenced by students' age and grade level. Sapungan and Sapungan (2014) documented the evolution of parental involvement from basic assistance to deeper engagement, which positively affects student behavior and achievement. However, Ochoa and Torre (2014) highlighted the persistence of corporal punishment in Filipino households—often linked to poverty and stress—advocating for culturally sensitive, holistic interventions that address both discipline and broader parental stressors while promoting positive parenting practices and bidirectional parent-child dynamics.

The close connection between responsive parenting and academic success is well-supported by studies like Nokali et al. (2017), which show that engaged parents enhance children's cognitive and social development. Research from the National Institute of Child Health and Development and other US institutions underscores that parental presence boosts confidence, classroom engagement, and positive school attitudes (Hara et al., 2016; Topor et al., 2017). Harvard scholars emphasize academic and cognitive socialization as key parental influences, with middle-income mothers often playing a prominent tutoring role (Bempechat, 2016).

Examining specific academic outcomes, Ashin and Sahim (2018) found in Tabuk City, Kalinga, that parental involvement is vital not only for academic performance in Mathematics but also for character formation. Their study showed that employed parents tend to be more engaged in schoolwork assistance compared to farmers and business owners, with greater involvement correlating with higher grades and better decision-making in children.

Broader meta-analyses and studies confirm these findings: Axford et al. (2019) demonstrated that warm, authoritative parenting predicts better academic achievement, whereas harsh or neglectful parenting correlates with poorer outcomes. Hara and Burke (2018) linked structured parental involvement to improvements in literacy and emotional health, while Ribeiro et al. (2021) highlighted pandemic challenges in balancing work and educational support. Davis (2021) confirmed parents' positive influence on grades and academic motivation. Camacho (2018) noted that child well-being and discipline are influenced by socioeconomic stressors, while Ashim and Ahmed (2018) found school location and parental involvement significantly affect mathematics achievement in Assam, India. Finally, Ates (2021) affirmed through meta-analysis that parental involvement universally benefits academic success, though effectiveness varies by contextual and demographic factors.

Together, these interconnected studies emphasize that parental involvement—shaped by cultural, socioeconomic, and contextual factors—is a foundational determinant of students’ academic achievement and emotional development, underscoring the critical need for supportive, adaptive strategies that engage families and schools alike.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on two key theories. The first is Epstein’s Framework of Parent Involvement (1992), which outlines six types of family-school-community partnerships: parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and collaborating with the community. Each type represents a unique way parents can engage in their children’s education, from creating supportive home environments to actively participating in school affairs and utilizing community resources. Supporting this, Gravells (2023) and Silberman (1970) emphasize the role of the parent as a facilitator of learning—one who motivates and supports the child without being the sole source of instruction. As facilitators, parents help create positive learning environments and encourage their children to learn through experience, fostering independence and critical thinking.

The second theoretical foundation is Thorndike’s Law of Effect, which posits that behavior followed by positive outcomes is likely to be repeated, while behavior followed by negative consequences is less likely to recur. This trial-and-error learning process strengthens the connection between stimulus and response through reinforcement. The study applies this principle to parental involvement, suggesting that positive reinforcement from parents—through support, praise, or consistent involvement—encourages desirable academic behaviors in children. Thus, the framework of this study integrates both Epstein’s typology and Thorndike’s behavioral theory, asserting that active and supportive parental involvement significantly contributes to students’ academic success in a blended learning environment.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality in relation to learners’ academic performance in a Private School in a large school Division in the central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality according to the area of home learning environment, learner’s motivation, and parental tutoring; 2) the level of learners’ academic performance; 3) the significant relationship between the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality and the level of learners’ academic performance; and 4) the significant relationship between the level of parental involvement in blended learning modality and learners’ level of academic performance.

Methodology

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive, comparative-correlational research design to examine the level of parental involvement in modular distance learning and its relation to learners’ academic performance. The descriptive approach is suited for identifying current conditions, relationships, and trends without influencing the subjects (Shuttleworth, 2016), while the correlational design explores the relationship between two variables and the comparative aspect compares groups to explain differences (Desai, 2017). Combining these methods allows for a comprehensive understanding of the present situation, considering both current factors and relevant past influences, thereby providing valuable data to inform recommendations.

Study Respondents

The respondents in this study were the 200 parents of a Private School in a large-sized school Division in the central Philippines whose learners were enrolled for the school year 2020-2021. According to Alchemer (2022), Purposive sampling is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. It is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing population members to participate in their surveys.

Instruments

A self-made questionnaire, validated by three education experts through face and content validation, was used to collect data, consisting of two parts: demographic information and a 30-item assessment of parental involvement in

blended learning across home environment, motivation, and tutoring, rated on a 1-to-5 scale from "almost never" to "always." Secondary data on academic performance were sourced from the Schools' Progress Report Card for the 2020–2021 school year, with ratings ranging from Outstanding to Did Not Meet Expectations. The instrument's validity was confirmed with a mean score of 4.56 ("Excellent"), while reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha with a coefficient of 0.731 ("Acceptable") from a pilot test involving 30 parents outside the study sample, indicating the questionnaire was both valid and reliable for this research.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher prepared a letter addressed to the Public Schools District Supervisor. This is to give her notice about the study and ask permission to conduct the study at a specified time and date. The approved copies will be attached to the three separate letters addressed to the school head.

The researcher administered the questionnaires to the respondents through a survey form. The questionnaires were requested to be answered by the parents and then were retrieved and tabulated. The raw scores were encoded in a formatted Excel file before it was submitted to the statistician for final tabulation, analysis, and interpretation according to the specific problem and hypotheses set forth in this investigation. The researcher assured the respondents that their identities and responses were kept confidential.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of Parental Involvement in blended learning modality according to the following areas: home learning environment, learners' motivation, and parental tutoring.

Objective No. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the learners' academic performance level.

Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of parental involvement in blended learning modality when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Objective No. 4 used the relational analytical scheme and Spearman rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of parental involvement in blended learning modality and learners' level of academic performance.

Ethical Consideration

Since the respondents of the study are parents and the research instrument was distributed in person, it was then an advantage for the researcher to discuss the nature of her study with the parents and the need for their cooperation and participation. The data collection with the respondents was also set according to the respondents' convenience and availability, and the researcher was able to gather outright and start tallying. There was an open conversation with the respondents, and the researcher was able to accommodate the questions raised by the respondents. The researcher strictly observed concealment and uprightness in conducting this study.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in the Areas of Home Learning Environment, Learners' Motivation, and Parental Tutoring

Table 1

Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Home Learning Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. clean the house so that it will be good for studying.	4.55	Very High Level
2. provide books and other reading materials at home.	4.26	High Level
3. make sure that the study area at home is well-ventilated.	4.39	High Level
4. make sure that our home is a safe study place for my children's modular learning.	4.39	High Level
5. provide all the support for the study of my child inside our home.	4.35	High Level
6. placed ample lighting in my child's study area.	4.33	High Level
7. put my child's study area in a quiet and noise-free area.	4.32	High Level

8. put internet connected at home for my child's research and class purposes.	3.97	High Level
9. strictly enforce the study and play time rule at home for my child.	4.17	High Level
10. teach my child how to study his/her lessons based on priorities.	4.31	High Level
Overall Mean	4.30	High Level

As illustrated in Table 1, on the Parental Involvement in blended learning modality in the area of home learning environment, the overall mean was 4.30 interpreted as "high level."

Item no. 1 was assessed by parent respondents as the highest mean of 4.55, which states, "As a parent, I clean the house so that it will be good for studying," interpreted as "very high level." however, item no. 8 was shown the lowest mean of 3.97 which says "As a parent, I put internet connected at home for my child's research and class purposes" also interpreted as "high level."

The results imply that in terms of home learning environment, parents are less supportive of providing internet connectivity at home for their children's research and class purposes.

This implication conforms to Liu et al. (2020) where the study amicably admitted that academic achievements and enhanced mental health are important educational goals that are within reach with the parents' involvement.

Table 2

Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Learners' Motivation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. motivate my child to independently study on his own.	4.31	High Level
2. read with my child.	3.96	High Level
3. allow my child to join online group study.	4.41	High Level
4. encourage my child to control usage of his/her cellphone during study hours.	4.36	High Level
5. encourage my child to avoid online games during study hours.	4.34	High Level
6. take time to explain difficult lessons to my child.	4.31	High Level
7. provide valid grounds and reasons to my child why he needs to work on his projects and performance tasks.	4.29	High Level
8. encourage my child to finish his assessments on time.	4.33	High Level
9. encourage my child to finish his projects and assignments.	4.48	High Level
10. provide clear reasons why my child should not play or roam around during study time.	4.31	High Level
Overall Mean	4.30	High Level

As presented in Table 2, on the Parental Involvement in blended learning modality in the area of learners' motivation, the overall mean was 4.30, interpreted as "high level."

Item no. 9 was assessed by parent respondents as the highest mean of 4.48, which states, "As a parent, I encourage my child to finish his projects and assignments," interpreted as "high level." however, item no. 2 shows the lowest mean of 3.96 which says "As a parent, I read with my child" also interpreted as "high level."

The results imply that in terms of learners' motivation, parents are less likely to read books with their children. There may be factors behind this result.

This implication agrees with Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) that parents constantly encourage their children to do well in school, achieve their career goals, plan future employment, and make basic preparations, among others.

Table 3

Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Parental Tutoring

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. provide for all the needs of my children, from personal to study needs.	4.44	High Level
2. always check if my child has a problem with his/her studies.	4.31	High Level
3. train my child to be more open to me with his/her problems in any subject.	4.40	High Level
4. spend quality time bonding with my child on weekends so we can talk about her schooling.	4.29	High Level
5. ask my child if there is something that he/she wants me to teach him/her.	4.33	High Level
6. teach my child how to manage his/her time.	4.44	High Level

7. teach my child how to do his assignments and projects.	4.43	High Level
8. spend ample time to help my child with these exams.	4.47	High Level
9. suggest ways and means to help my child complete his projects.	4.44	High Level
10. ask the teacher of my child if there is any lacking or unreturned modules.	4.47	High Level
Overall Mean	4.37	High Level

As shown in Table 3, on the Parental Involvement in blended learning modality in the area of parental tutoring, the overall mean was 4.37, interpreted as "high level."

Item numbers 8 and 10 were assessed by parent respondents as the highest mean of 4.47, which states, "As a parent, I spend ample time to help my child with these exams" and "ask the teacher of my child if there are any lacking or unreturned modules" both interpreted as "high level" while item no. 4 was the lowest mean of 4.29 which says "As a parent, I spend quality time to bond with my child on weekends so we can talk about her schooling" also interpreted as "high level."

The results imply that in terms of parental tutoring, parents have less time to go out with their children on weekends to share about their schooling. This may be due to work and other priorities.

This implication fits in Pek and Mee Mee's (2020) study in Malaysia, which states that parent involvement greatly influences their child's academic success. Although parental involvement is widely recognized in educational society, most parents report that they are still not effectively involved in their children's education, whether at school or home.

Level of Learners' Academic Performance

Table 4
Level of Learners' Academic Performance

Variable	Mean	Interpretation
Level of Learners' Academic Performance	85.74	Very Satisfactory

In Table 4, the Learners' Academic Performance level is "very satisfactory," with an overall mean of 85.74. This implies that the learners' grades are generally high.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in the Areas of Home Learning Environment, Learners' Motivation, and Parental Tutoring When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Table 5
Significant Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Home Learning Environment When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	91	97.39	4676.50	0.486	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	109	103.1				
Number of Siblings	Few	76	90.55	4054.50	0.026	0.05	Significant
	Many	124	108.80				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	126	96.90	4631.50	0.419	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	74	103.51				

As presented in Table 5, on variable highest educational attainment, the obtained Mann Whitney U test was 4676.50 with a p-value of 0.486, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to their highest educational attainment," and on the area, Home Learning Environment was accepted.

Regarding the number of siblings, the Mann-Whitney U Test was 4054.50 with a p-value of 0.026, which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the hypothesis states, "there is no

significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to their number of siblings." In the area, the Home Learning Environment was rejected.

Then, as to the average family monthly income, the obtained Mann Whitney U test was 4631.50 with a p-value of 0.419, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance and is thus interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to their average family monthly income," and on the area, Home Learning Environment was accepted.

This implies that the level of parental involvement in the Blended Learning Modality in the area of home learning environment when the parents are grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment and average family monthly income varies, but with sex, it does not vary.

Kalayci's (2018) findings also agree that such demographic characteristics as the level of education generally make no significant difference in parents' perceptions about parental involvement.

Table 6
Significant Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Learners' Motivation When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	91	101.80	4613.00	0.803	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	109	99.70				
Number of Siblings	Few	76	105.76	4312.00	0.313	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	124	97.27				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	126	105.80	4309.50	0.309	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	74	97.25				

As shown in Table6, on variable highest educational attainment, the obtained Mann Whitney U test was 4613.00 with a p-value of 0.803, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance and, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to their highest educational attainment" and on the area of Learners' Motivation was accepted.

As to the number of siblings, the obtained Mann-Whitney U Test was 4312.00 with a p-value of 0.313, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to their number of siblings" and on the area of Learners' Motivation was accepted.

Then, as to the average family monthly income, the obtained Mann Whitney U test was 4309.50 with a p-value of 0.309, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance and is thus interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to their average family monthly income" and on the area of learners' motivation was also accepted.

This implies that the level of parental involvement in the Blended Learning Modality in the area of learners' motivation when the parents are grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment, number of siblings, and average family monthly income does not vary.

Toggle (2020) confirms in her study that no significant differences exist in the variables of educational attainment and family income.

Table 7
Significant Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Parental Tutoring When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	91	94.82	3754.50	0.073		Not Significant
	Higher	109	110.06				
Number of Siblings	Few	76	90.51	3403.00	0.001	0.05	Significant
	Many	124	117.51				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	126	86.54	2903.00	0.000		Significant
	Higher	74	124.27				

As illustrated in Table 7, on variable highest educational attainment, the obtained Mann Whitney U test was 3754.50 with a p-value of 0.073, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance and is thus interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to their highest educational attainment," and on the area of Parental Tutoring was accepted.

However, as to the number of siblings, the obtained Mann-Whitney U Test was 3403.00 with a p-value of 0.001, which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and when compared according to their number of siblings," and in the area of parental tutoring, it was rejected.

As to the average family monthly income, the obtained Mann Whitney U test was 2903.00 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance, thus interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to their average family monthly income," and on the area of Parental Tutoring was also rejected.

This implies that the level of parental involvement in the Blended Learning Modality in the area of Parental Tutoring, when the parents are grouped and compared according to the number of siblings and average family monthly income, does not vary. Still, their highest educational attainment varies.

Naité (2021) negates the implication because, in his study, parental income level has no impact on the level of involvement in their children's education. However, the parents' educational level had a greater impact on parental involvement.

Relational Analysis Between the Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality and the Level of Learners' Academic Performance

Table 8
Relationship Between the Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality and the Level of Learners' Academic Performance

Correlates	N	rho	Level of Sig	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Parental Involvement in Blended Learning Modality	200	-0.106	0.05	0.135	Not Significant
Level of Learners' Performance	200				

The Spearman Rho's r-test result of -0.106 with a p-value of 0.135 showed significant difference existed between the levels of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality and the level of learners' Academic Performance. Their responses, therefore, did not vary when they were grouped according to the 3 areas and 3 variables.

Hence, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant relationship in the levels of parental involvement in Blended Learning Modality and the Level of Learners' Academic Performance, is accepted.

In other words, parents have a less varied level of involvement in the learners' academic performance. Differences could possibly occur, but only with minimal variations.

The findings by Quijano, Uy, and Franca (2023) confirm as indicated that there was no significant correlation between parental involvement and student performance.

Conclusions:

The study found that over half of the parents had completed high school, had three or more children, and earned a monthly income of Php 12,000 or less. Parental involvement in blended learning was generally rated high across all areas, with parental tutoring receiving the highest mean score, followed by the home learning environment and learners' motivation, which shared identical scores. High levels of involvement were consistent regardless of parents' education and number of siblings, while parents with higher incomes showed very high involvement specifically in parental tutoring. Learners' academic performance was rated very satisfactory overall. No significant differences were observed between parental involvement and learners' academic performance concerning parents' education, but significant differences appeared related to the number of siblings and family income in the home learning environment and motivation areas. The study concluded that while parental involvement is high, challenges such as limited internet access and time management exist, particularly in reading activities and weekend tutoring, highlighting the need for parental training and support. Recommendations include improving internet access for learners, encouraging weekly parent-child reading time, offering time management seminars for parents, and maintaining strong teacher-parent collaboration to sustain academic performance.

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References:

- Abd Rosyid, & Suyadi, S. (2022). Parental Guidance for Instilling Independence in Worship of Early Childhood in Bungbaruh Kadur Pamekasan. *Joyced: Journal of Early Childhood Education*, 2(1), 38–48. <https://doi.org/10.14421/joyced.2022.21-04>
- Agaton, C.B. and L.J. Cueto. (2021). Learning at home: Parents' lived experiences on distance learning during COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*. Vol. 10, No. 3. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1313094.pdf>
- Alchemer research Solutions. (2022). Purposive Sampling 101. <https://www.alchemer.com/resources/blog/purposive-sampling-101/>
- Ashim, B. and Ahmed. S. (2018). Effects of Parental Involvement on Secondary School Students' Mathematics Achievement in Assam, India. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED588191.pdf>
- Ateş, A (2021). The Relationship Between Parental Involvement in Education and Academic Achievement: A Meta-analysis Study. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, Vol. 11, No. 3, 2021, 50-66
- Axford, N., Berry, V., Lloyd, J., Moore, D., Rogers, M., Hurst, A., Blockley, K., Durkin, H. and Minton, J. (2019) *How Can Schools Support Parents' Engagement in their Children's Learning? Evidence from Research and Practice*. London: Education Endowment Foundation.
- Camacho, G.B. (2018). Number of children in a household and child well-being. <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/3238/323856298002/html/>
- Davis, R.E. (2021). *Early Adolescent Relationships and Academic Achievement*. University of Texas at Austin. https://sites.utexas.edu/psychonors18/files/2021/12/RachelDavis_HonorsThesis2021.pdf
- Desai, M.K. (2017). Causal comparative research. Slideshare. Scribd Company. <https://www.slideshare.net/mirakdesai/causal-comparative-research-71596992>
- Duriscic, M., & Bunjevac, M. (2017). Parental Involvement as a Important Factor for Successful Education. *CEPS Journal*, 7(3), 139–143. <https://doi.org/EJ1156936>
- Epstein, J.L. *School and Family Partnerships*. Report No. 6; Center on Families, Communities, Schools, and Children's Learning, Publications, The Johns Hopkins University: Baltimore, MD, USA, 1992; p. 21218.12.
- Epstein, J.L. *School/Family/Community Partnerships: Caring for the Children We Share*. *Phi Delta Kappan* 2010,92, 81–96.[CrossRef}
- Gravells, A. (2023). *Learning Theories*. <https://www.anngravells.com/information/learning-theories>
- Guo, X. (2018). Gender Differences in how family income and parental education relate to children's reading. *National Institutes of Health.gov*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>

- Hara S.R. and D.J. Burke. (2018). Parent Involvement: The Key to Improved Student Achievement. <https://www.adi.org/journal/ss01/chapters/chapter16-hara&burke.pdf>
- Yu , H. ., Asistido, M. T., & Bautista, M. (2024). Difficulties Encountered by Vocational Students in the Online-Learning Modality. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRIS)*, 1(5), 481-489. <https://risejournals.org/index.php/imjrise/article/view/443>
- Jorban, Mohamad & Cachón-Zagalaz, Javier & Mecías, Marcos & Navarro Paton, Ruben. (2024). Facilitators of and Barriers to Inclusive Education in the Arab Community of Israel: The Parents' Perspective. *Education Sciences*. 14. 525. 10.3390/educsci14050525.
- Kalaycı, G., & Öz, H. (2018). Parental involvement in English language education: Understanding parents' perceptions. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 5(4), 832-847. <http://iojet.org/index.php/IOJET/article/view/447/296>
- Liu, Y., m.F. Sulaimani, and J.E. Henning. (2020). The Significance of Parental Involvement in the Development in Infancy. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1268016.pdf>
- Main, P. (2023). Thorndike's Theory. <https://www.structural-learning.com/post/thorndikes-theory>
- Methodist University. (2023). Conceptual Framework: The Facilitative Teacher. <https://www.methodist.edu/academics/business-technology-professional-studies/teacher-education/conceptual-framework/>
- Mizunoya, Suguru & Brossard, Matt & Kamei, Akito & Mishra, Sakshi & Reuge, Nicolas. (2020). Parental Involvement in Children's Learning.
- Naite, Ibrahima. (2021). *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* 690 012064
DOI 10.1088/1755-1315/690/1/012064
- Quigley. E. (2023). What is blended learning?
<https://www.learnupon.com/blog/what-is-blended-learning>
- Quijano , H. U., Uy , A. C., & Franca , G. C. (2023). Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of Grade 12 Students. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 47(4), 11–17. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2023/v47i41029>
- Ribeiro, L. M., Cunha, R. S., Silva, M. C., Carvalho, M., & Vital, M. L. (2021). Parental Involvement during Pandemic Times: Challenges and Opportunities. *Education Sciences*, 11(6), 302. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11060302>
- Salalc, L.M. and J.U. Florida. (2022). Epstein Model of Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of Learners. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*. Vol. 11, No. 2
<file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/6398-14990-1-PB.pdf>
- Scott, M. P. (2023). Household Income: What it is and how to calculate it.
https://www.investopedia.com/terms/h/household_income
- Seong Pek, Lim & Mee Mee, Rita. (2020). PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT ON CHILD'S EDUCATION AT HOME DURING SCHOOL LOCKDOWN. *JHSS (JOURNAL OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL STUDIES)*. 4. 192-196. 10.33751/jhss.v4i2.2502.
- Shao, M., W. He, L. Zhao, and Y. S. Su. (2021). The Influence of Parental Involvement on Parent Satisfaction: The Moderating Effect of Parental Educational Level and the Number of Children. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.752802/full>
- Togle, B.L. (2020). Awareness and Involvement of Parents to School Activities in Relation to the Learners' Academic Performance. An unpublished Dissertation. STI West Negros University. Bacolod City.